

Differences in Explanation of Forestry Terms

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Abstract: This study explores differences in the interpretation of forestry terms in different contexts, including academic, industrial, and public discourse. By analyzing the definitions and usage of key terms, we highlight how terminology can affect understanding and communication between stakeholders. The study identified gaps in term clarity, context-specific meanings, and implications for policy development and education. It also highlights the importance of standardized definitions to enhance cooperation and promote sustainable forestry practices. Ultimately, this work aims to develop a more unified approach to forestry terminology that will benefit both professionals and the general public.

Keywords: Forest terminology, human, society, definitions, online dictionaries.

Introduction

In Uzbekistan, in the last few decades, there have been drastic changes in the relationship between society and forests. Due to climate and environmental changes, the public is increasingly concerned about the country's forests. Previously, forests were considered a part of nature in general, but they were considered primarily as a source of wood not only in the world but also in our country. Now, society and people value forests as places for various ecological and social needs, as well as places for recreation, use, and sports. These changes require more communication from people in the community in implementing forest management and conservation practices. However, to be effective in communication, it appears that people and society must have a deep understanding of forest terminology, and today, in the application of this terminology, the use of the lexicon of the field is rampant, and sometimes deliberately wrong. In the introduction to their "Forestry Dictionary", German scholars clearly stated the need for "clear definitions and explanations" [1] to clearly describe the use of terms in individual languages.

2. Changes in society and the impact of current problems on the language

Changing public attitudes towards forests are due to many interacting factors. Values have changed as a result of attempts by the population and their elected representatives to urbanize the countryside, forests, and other rural areas, to accelerate the process of urbanization. Advanced forms of forest information (real and comprehensible), including vivid images of live and wildlife there, have expanded and are still expanding as a result of television, the Internet, and social media. However, there is a growing concern among the population about the preservation of forests and the prevention of environmental pollution. Undoubtedly, there are also concerns about habitat loss, particularly deforestation, and the fate of endangered wildlife and plants. It is also true that there are many known reasons for such anxiety and

that the human factor is at the root of them. There is also a perception that forests are being mismanaged due to the overuse of logging in forests, resulting in a partial decline in confidence in professions such as foresters, foresters, forest inspectors, and forest wardens. In this process, one of the world's scientists, Nerida Puentes Álvarez, said the following: “terminology, that is, the terminology of the field, is intended to understand the semantic and conceptual features of sustainable development of forests, and language and science education programs are intended to be ready for the problems that will be faced in the future” [6] means the relevance of the issue.

3. Relevance of forest to terminology

In the preface to “Dictionary of Forestry”, the author has already emphasized the problem of translation of technical terms and the need to provide definitions, and explanations to clearly describe the use of terms in individual languages. Provided feedback on the creation of a database of multilingual forest terminology. It should be emphasized that the increase of public interest in forestry issues and their discussion of all cases is welcomed by the state and society. But discussions are difficult when certain terms are used inconsistently. The following term is analyzed as an example.

In Uzbek: Bokira Urmon (tegilmagan urmon), inson aralashuvi bilan umuman buzilmagan, tuzlanishi bilan tabiiy rivojlanishni saqlab qoladigan huddir. Tuproq, iqlim, butun o‘simlik va odam dunyosi hamda hayot yaralari yog‘och tayyorlanish, chorva boqish yoki boshqa vosita yoki bilvosita antropogen jarayonlar natijasida buzil va o‘zgarmagan o‘rmon demakdir.

In English: Virgin Forest (untouched forest). Areas (or forests) that have never been disturbed by human intervention, showing natural development in structure and dynamics. The soil, climate, entire flora and fauna, and life processes have not been disturbed or changed by timber management, cattle grazing, or other direct or indirect anthropogenic influences [7].

In Russian: Девственный лес (нетронутый лес). Территории (или леса), которые никогда не были нарушены вмешательством человека, демонстрирующие естественное развитие в структуре и динамике. Почва, климат, вся флора и фауна, а также жизненные процессы не были нарушены или изменены лесозаготовками, выпасом скота или другими прямыми, или косвенными антропогенными воздействиями.

In German: Ursprünglicher Wald (unberührter Wald). Gebiete (oder Wälder), die nie durch menschliche Eingriffe gestört wurden und eine natürliche Entwicklung in Struktur und Dynamik aufweisen. Der Boden, das Klima, die gesamte Flora und Fauna und die Lebensprozesse wurden nicht durch Holzwirtschaft, Viehbeweidung oder andere direkte oder indirekte anthropogene Einflüsse gestört oder verändert.

This inconsistency in the use of the term virgin forest is controversial. Interestingly, this term is not appropriate for the Uzbek language, therefore, the fact that the territory of Uzbekistan is not very rich in forest zones and that there are no lands and forests that have not been affected by anthropogenic factors raises a clear doubt. From the point of view of the Uzbek language, it is natural that this term is controversial. For example, when a search for virgin forests is made from the Wikipedia database, several of the following words are found: 1) ancient forest; 2) virgin forest; 3) primary forest; 4) late seral forest; 5) options such as old growth forest were presented. What are the annotations that represent the variety of options? More than a third of the world's forests are primary forests [8]. These old-growth features include a variety of tree-related structures that provide habitat for a variety of wildlife that increase the biodiversity of the forest ecosystem. Virgin forests are old forests that have

never been cut down.

There are 1.11 billion hectares of primary forests remaining in the world, with Brazil, Canada and Russia accounting for more than half (61%) of the world's primary forests. The area of primary forest has decreased by 81 million hectares since 1990, but the rate of loss between 2010 and 2020 has more than halved compared to the previous decade [4].

Old-growth forests are valuable for economic reasons and for the ecosystem services they provide [4]. In addition, old-growth forests are more efficient at storing carbon than newly planted forests and fast-growing timber plantations, so forest conservation is important for climate change mitigation[10]. As conclusion of our above opinion, it can be said that all the information obtained on the explanation of the term “virgin forest” is based on the scientific literature and sources of foreign scientists.

At the same time, people's and society's interest in managing the remaining forest lands and their fate has increased. Calls to preserve the remaining ancient, virgin, old, perennial trees can be heard in all corners of the world. Nature conservation organizations and groups rightly want to preserve ancient forests. That is why key terms such as ancient and virgin forest are not sufficiently defined. H. Hyde Lund emphasizes that “it is impossible to use unknown definitions when quoting terms”[3].

However, inconsistent use of forestry terms is also common in the profession. For example, there is no clear understanding of what fundamental terms such as forest exactly mean or what exactly the field of forestry covers. Even the term “forester” is difficult to define because there are semantic differences between terms such as “professional forester”, “forest owner” and “forest supervisor”. For example, in the German language, the repetition of terms in terms of content and meaning, that is, the large number of synonymous words, defines the aspects of the German language that are different from other languages. For example, the table below shows the differences.

Table 1. Synonyms of forest guard in four languages

In Uzbek	in English	in Russian	in German
o‘rmon qorovuli	forest guard	лесник	der Forstaufseher
o‘rmon qorovuli	forest guard	лесник	der Waldaufseher
o‘rmon qorovuli	forest guard	лесник	der Waldheger
o‘rmon qorovuli	forest guard	лесник	der Waldhüter

It turned out that the term “forest guard”, which is expressed by one word in Uzbek, English, and Russian languages, can be used in four different synonyms only in German, and there are no lexical differences between them. In context, in speech, and in scholarly sources, all four German variants of the term forest ranger have the same meaning.

It is therefore not surprising that as forestry expands to encompass new concepts that are difficult to define, such as ecosystem management, sustainability and forest health, the scope of terms also expands. Therefore, when the same terms are used with different meanings, confusion is bound to arise in the development of public opinion, the interpretation of management plans, and the development of forest policy. Similar confusion occurs when the same condition is expressed using different terms.

Here, the compatibility and incompatibility of forestry terms used in English with other languages were analyzed as follows. For example, the word *Mortality* [11] directly means “death” in the Uzbek language, and naturally, it is necessary to determine which signs and characteristics of the term forestry are associated with the word. Therefore, it is appropriate to use the term “natural losses”. Natural loss is an event that occurs as a result of a natural disaster, and refers to a natural process or phenomenon that can affect the environment, such

as earthquakes, hurricanes, droughts. It is known that nature experiences many natural losses and it is important to use the term “*natural losses*”. This term is expressed in other languages, for example, in Russian as “смертность”, in German as “*Mortalität*”, meaning “*death*” in medicine, and here the aspects of the word's dependence on forestry terms are not obvious.

Inconsistencies in such comments are also observed in German and English. For example, *Holzboden* - *forest land*. In English we can understand it in a general sense as “*forest land*”. Similarly, *Forsteinerichtung* is a term for forest management, in German it is a compound word, actually the word *Einrichtung* means to equip, and furnish, but in this case, these meanings belong to the words *ausrichten*, and *ordnen*. *Forsteinerichtung* is a term related to forestry activities, meaning leveling, regulation, and sustainable management of forestry [2].

It is often better not to translate words or technical terms that cannot be translated into other languages, but to translate them into another language in their own form, with additional definitions and explanations. For example, the word “*tilib qo'yish*” is found among the forest terms. In German, *die Abharzung* has the same meaning as “*подсочка*” in Russian and “*slice*” in English. For a broader interpretation of this word, it is appropriate to quote its following definition: “*slicing the bark of a tree to extract its juice*”.

It is important to compare such terms in the Uzbek language with other languages. For example:

In Uzbek: қўлтиқ куртаклар

In English: the axillary bud

In Russian: пазушная почка

In German: die Achselknospe

The pictures show the emergence of axillary buds from the leaf, leaf band and stem.

If there is a difficulty in understanding the term axillary buds, or if there is a natural need for an explanation despite the provision of pictorial explanations, then the phrase “*buds that appear between a leaf band or a branch*” is included. In many cases, providing such explanations eliminates misunderstandings, the “*mood*” of internationalism found in terms, and even the direct expression of words, terms, and lexicon that are understandable only to certain fields. Hundreds of such terms can be found in forest terminology, and below only lexicons in the Uzbek language are cited.

Table 2. Definition of terms

Terms	Definition of terms
akklimatizatsiya	acclimatization, adaptation to new climate, new conditions, getting used to
to'psa	the lower thick side of a tree adjacent to the root
deformatsiya	change or alteration of form
daraxt zamazkasi	adhesive mixture used to cover cracks and crevices
tovoqsoy	It is a deep, plate-like land surrounded by high hills and mountains

4. Problems of terminology development

One of the challenges in developing forestry dictionaries is deciding what constitutes forestry. Forestry was originally defined mainly in terms of timber production and utilization of forest products. Today, however, the field of forestry has expanded to focus more on other attributes of the forest, including not only trees, but important forest components such as soil, forest vegetation, wildlife, water, and the environment. Forestry now includes biological, management, production, and other social aspects. Thus, the distinction between the vocabulary of forestry and the vocabulary of natural resources is increasingly difficult. Also, on the one hand, there are difficulties in determining to what extent specific terms related to the details of forest science within the scope of forest soils, forest entomology, forest tree physiology, forestry, etc., should be included in the forestry vocabulary. On the other hand, the publication of regulated terms raises special considerations. Traditionally, dictionaries are published in book form, become obsolete immediately, and their usefulness diminishes over time. Characteristically, dictionaries are not often revised due to the magnitude and scope of the task and the costs involved. A potential solution to this is to publish dictionaries electronically and make them available online. This has the great advantage of being easy to use, searchable for any term, and constantly updated. Terms in electronic dictionaries can be easily revised as definitions are improved through use and new terms are added.

5. Conclusion

Current disadvantages of electronic dictionaries include, in some cases, the inability to obtain copyright permission from some sources for individual terms to be published electronically. In addition, there are concerns about whether electronic publications can cover the costs of development, review, and compilation. Perhaps some users prefer to have dictionaries in both book and electronic form. However, the uncertainty as to whether publishers will be able to cover publication costs and obtain profit margins precludes the preferred alternative of making dictionaries available in both formats.

References

1. Griess, O. Forstwirtschaftliche Informatik. Allgemeine Forstzeitung, 87. Jg., Folge 9, Wien 1976.
2. Griess O., Kurth H., Unterthiner G. Forsteinrichtung As Against Forest Management / Difficulties with the compilation of a multilingual terminology. Vienna, 2002.
3. Gyde Lund H. Coming to Terms with Politicians and Definitions. Vienna, 2002.
4. Maloof, Joan. *Nature's Temples: The Complex World of Old-Growth Forests* (Englisch). Timber Press, 16-noyabr 2016-yil. ISBN 978-1-60469-728-5.

5. Matsumoto M. Proposal of A Multilingual Forest Terminology Database Designed for Western and Non-Western Languages. Vienna, 2002.
6. Puentes Alvarez N. Terminology as a way to communicate values sustainable forest development: vision of the world in the 21st century. Vienna, 2002.
7. Schuck A., Päivinen R., Hytönen T., Pajari B. *Compilation of Forestry Terms and Definitions. European Forest Institute, Internal Report No. 6, 2002.*
8. *The State of the World's Forests 2020. In brief – Forests, biodiversity and people.* Rome: FAO, 2020 — 9-bet. DOI: 10.4060/ca8985en. ISBN 978-92-5-132707-4.
9. Wirth, Christian. *Old-Growth Forests: Function, Fate and Value* (Englisch). Springer Science & Business Media, 7-iyul 2009-yil. ISBN 978-3-540-92706-8.
10. https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Qadimgi_o%27rmon
11. *Encyclopedia Britannica* (<http://www.britannica.com/>)